

Interaction of Montmorillonite Clay and Trace Element Cations. Dissociation of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} Ions from the Respective Clays at Different Degrees of Saturation

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A significant correlation has been shown to exist between the pH of the medium and the amounts of 'free' Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions in Co-H- and Ni-H-clay suspensions. The regression analysis yields the equation $Y = 14.232 - 2.797 X$, where Y is the amount of Co^{2+} or Ni^{2+} in m.e./100g. and X is the pH with a correlation coefficient of 0.7802, significant at 0.1% level.

As reported in the literature¹, the trace element content of soils depends, besides other factors, on the pH of the soil. In acid soils, for example, the soluble copper may be lost through leaching². Bryan³ states that the copper deficiency in Florida citrus is more prevalent on acid than on alkaline soils. The deficiency of manganese is seldom due to the deficiency in total manganese content and rarely occurs on soils more acid⁴ than pH 6.5.

As regards availability, the soil reaction is perhaps the most important factor. Nair and Mehta⁵ have found that the acid-soluble zinc content of some Western Indian soils decreases with increase of pH. This supports the observations of earlier workers⁶⁻⁸. Massey⁹ showed that the uptake of zinc by corn plants was negatively correlated with pH and positively correlated with the dithizone-extractable zinc from the soil.

An attempt has been made to ascertain the relation, if any, between the 'free' cation content and the pH of clays having varying degrees of unsaturation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The residues of Ni-H- and Co-H-clays, remaining after exchange reaction of saturated Ni- and Co-clays with various concentrations of H_2SO_4 (cf. Basu and Mukherjee¹⁰), were washed twice to remove the adhering metal ions with either slightly acidulated water or

1. Vinogradov, "The Geochemistry of Rare and Dispersed Chemical Elements in Soil", 2nd ed., Consultants Bureau, Inc., New York, 1959.
2. Purvis, "Agricultural Chemistry", Vol. II, edited by Frazer, D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., 1951, p. 324.
3. Florida Dept. Agr. (New series), 1940, 93.
4. *Soil Sci.*, 1950, **87**, 155.
5. Camp, *ibid.*, 1945, **60**, 157.
6. Lott, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1938, **3**, 115.
7. Pesch, *Soil Sci.*, 1941, **51**, 473.
8. Wear and Sommer, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1948, **12**, 143.
9. *Soil Sci.*, 1957, **83**, 123.

with ordinary distilled water. The clays were then suspended in acidulated or ordinary water in the respective cases and made to a known volume. The suspensions were preserved in well-stoppered Jena bottles. In the same manner, the residues of Ni-H- and Co-H-clays, obtained by equilibrating the saturated clays against H-resin (cf. Basu and Mukherjee¹⁰), were also kept in well-stoppered Jena bottles.

TABLE

System.	H ⁺ ion used for exchange	Exchangeable metal ion (by diff.) ¹⁰ (m.c./100g.).	Clay content.	Aging time.	pH.	Cation content of the supernatant liquid (m.c./100g.).	
	Form.	Conc. (S).					
Ni-H-clay	H ₂ SO ₄	0.5	52.2	0.43%	21 month	4.0*	4.1
		1.0	43.0	0.29	24	4.7	1.2
		2.0	35.7	0.43	21	3.5*	3.3
		2.0	35.7	0.29	24	4.5	0.9
		3.0	32.4	0.43	21	3.4*	5.5
		4.0	..	0.29	24	4.3	0.9
	H-resin	6.0	..	0.29	24	4.2	0.6
		1.5	44.8	0.58	19	3.7	4.0
		2.0	41.0	0.20	10	3.6	4.7
		2.5	36.3	0.29	19	3.7	4.5
Ni-clay	..	..	87.5	2.17	44	4.0	0.8
Co-H-clay	H ₂ SO ₄	0.5	53.0	0.45	20	4.8	1.9
		1.0	46.5	0.29	22	4.3*	2.2
		1.0	46.5	.290	20	4.5	1.3
		1.5	41.2	0.29	20	4.7	1.2
		2.0	39.2	0.20	22	4.2*	2.2
		2.0	39.2	0.45	20	4.4	1.2
		3.0	33.0	0.20	22	4.1*	2.2
		3.0	33.0	0.29	20	4.3	2.0
	H-resin	0.5	52.8	0.57	14	4.0	2.7
		1.0	48.0	0.24	21	4.3	5.3
		1.0	48.0	0.29	14	4.0	3.1
		1.5	44.2	0.24	21	4.0	3.8
		1.5	44.2	0.29	14	3.9	3.1
		2.0	38.4	0.29	14	3.9	2.7
Mn-H-clay	H-resin	0.5	43.4	0.67	3 days	3.7	1.3
		1.0	36.0	0.67	..	3.4	1.3
		1.0	36.0	0.67	..	3.4	1.0
		1.5	30.3	0.67	..	3.3	1.0
		2.0	29.5	0.67	..	3.3	1.5
		3.0	28.7	0.67	..	3.1	0.7
Mn-clay	..	..	59.0	1.34	20	5.0	0.8

*The clay, after washing, was taken up and its volume was made with acidulated water (pH 4). For others, water was used.

¹⁰ Basu and Mukherjee, this Journal, 1966, 43, 245.

After a period of about 1½ to 2 years, the pH values of the suspensions were measured. The suspensions were then centrifuged and the clear supernatant liquid obtained in each case was analysed for the metal ion content.

The data are recorded in Table I and graphically presented in Fig 1. The table also shows somewhat similar data on some Mn-H-clays which have been discussed (*vide infra*).

DISCUSSION

The data on pH and 'free' Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ contents of the Ni-H- and Co-H-clays are considered homogeneous and may be subjected to regression analysis. The equation is $Y = 14.232 - 2.707X$, where Y is the amount of Co²⁺ or Ni²⁺ in m.e./100g. and X is the pH. A highly significant negative correlation between pH and the Ni²⁺ as well as the Co²⁺ contents of the supernatant liquids has been found, the correlation coefficient being 0.7662, significant at 0.1% level. This would imply that the metal ions, viz., Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺, 'dissociate' from the clays, the extent of 'dissociation' being largely dependent on the equilibrium pH.

FIG. 1. Variation of dissociated Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺ ions with pH of clays of different degrees of saturation.

The data on Mn-H-clay, referred to above, were obtained in a slightly different manner. In the case of Ni- and Co-clays (exchanged with H-resin), the resin after equi-

bration was withdrawn and the resulting partially desaturated clays were allowed to 'age' in bottles for about 1½ to 2 years after which the pH values were measured and the centrifugates were analysed. In the case of the Mn-clays, on the other hand, immediately after the resin was withdrawn, when the exchange equilibrium was attained, the resulting partially desaturated clays were subjected to pH determination and an analysis of the supernatant liquid was made. 'Free' Mn²⁺ was found to be present in the liquid. It is interesting to note that the pH values of all the partially desaturated Mn-H-clays, which were not allowed to 'age' properly, are lower than even that of the H-clay itself (2.7% suspensions have a pH 3.9), which has, as usual, been allowed to 'age' for a considerable period before pH measurement.

It may not be irrelevant to mention in this connection the work of Slabaugh¹¹ who observed a strong acid character of montmorillonite, like that of mineral acids, when the clay was passed through a column of H-resin and immediately titrated. This strong acid character gave place to the usual weak acid character on 'aging'. Recently Mitra and Singh¹² also observed a strong acid character of acid-washed clays which were kept in suspension in nonaqueous medium in order probably to prevent 'aging'. On suspending in water and allowing to 'age', the weak acid character shows up.

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12. *Naturwiss.*, 1959, 46, 319.